

MANAGING EDUCATION IN A DEPRESSED ECONOMY FOR NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The focus of this paper is on the management of education with particular reference to funding schools in a depressed economy and its implication for National Development and Societal growth. Education is very vital to the increasing pace of social, political and economic development of nation. Management of education refers to the process of planning, organizing, directing, staffing, co-coordinating, budgeting for and reporting on the education system. Education is an instrument for ensuring national development, which can only be achieved through proper planning and administration. The management of education sector is faced with a depressed economy that affects its proper funding; Hence, the possibility of Government control measures such as cutting down expenditure which may affect the statutory allocation to the education sector. The paper reviewed management of education and sources of funds in a depressed economy. The paper therefore, concludes that proper management of education is required in order to maintain and improve the standard in the education sector in Nigeria. This paper therefore suggests that Government should devote a sizeable percent of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to funding the education sector because education can help shape the economy of the country for the assurance of national development.

Keywords: Managing education, depressed economy, National Development.

Introduction

Education is described as an instrument par excellence for ensuring National development (FGN, 2014). This can only be achieved through effective management and administration. The provision of management and administration of educational system is the responsibility of Government at all levels (Local Government, State and Federal Governments). The National Policy on Education (NPE) has spelt out five main national goals of Nigeria which have been endorsed as the necessary foundation for the national policy on education as follows:

- ✓ A free and democratic society
- ✓ A just and egalitarian society
- ✓ A united, strong and self- reliant nation
- ✓ A great and dynamic economy
- ✓ A land full of bright opportunities for all citizens.

All these above are the state or near state of national development. Management of education in 21st century has witnessed active participation by non-governmental agencies, communities and individuals as well as government intervention. One of the misfortunes in our present day society is the depressed economy which has great negative implications on national development. Education is an instrument for ensuring social political and economic stability of a nation so there is need to ensure proper funding and management of education. Hence, it is important to look at educational management and economic depression in relation to poor funding in Nigerian schools.

There is no gainsaying the fact that education is very vital to the pace of social, political and economic development of any nation. This is why most nations of the world strive to devote a sizeable proportion of their Gross National Income to develop the educational sector. In Nigeria, between 7.6% and 9.9% of our annual expenditure is devoted to education (UNESCO, 2000). Management of education refers to the process of planning, organizing, directing, staffing, coordinating, budgeting for and reporting on the education system.

Some countries world-over now pay adequate attention to education. This is to enable the sector meet with the challenges of the 21st century and most essentially the world-wide revolution in the area of information communication technology (Odufowokan, 2007). Accordingly, the proportion of the Gross National Product (GNP), earmarked for education in Nigeria and other countries of the world has increased significantly. The world bank estimates reflects the proportion of Nigeria's GNP devoted to education increased on the average from 2.3 percent in 1960 to 4.5 percent in 1984, and the proportion of the national government budget rose from 11.7 percent in 1960 to 16.1 percent in 1984 (Famade, 2014). It rose further from 2.9 percent in 1990 to 3.7 percent in 1991 and from 3.7 percent in 1991 to 8.7 percent in 1992 and 15.28 percent in 1993 respectively. In a study carried out by Aghenta (1989) and Durosaro (1997) they evaluated that education consumes between 16 and 22 per cent of states annual income and between

19.8 and 50.8 percent of the annual income of the individuals.

The economic depression brought about by the oil glut of the 1980s till date still has its grip on the educational sector. Indisputably, the sector has not recovered fully from the ending effect it had. Since then, there has been increasing evidence of financial constraints coupled with the proportion of government budget and GNP available to education financing. Contributing to these, is the escalating cost of financing education which has placed the government in a sort of serious dilemma! This paper analyzed how education can be managed in depressed economy to be able to contribute to the national development.

The expansion witnessed in the last two decades in the Nigerian education system has no equal. This was as a result of increased number of schools, size of schools, physical facilities, enrolment, curriculum, personnel and policy decisions. Seemingly, the financial resource allocation to the sector is nominal in terms of naira and kobo. This is because, the business of education had been based on the view that education is an investment yielding dividend by way of producing the much needed manpower and other national benefits accruing to an educated person. However, financial resources (money) available to the government have failed to cope with the growth and demands of the sector in recent times (Okebukola, 2008). Financial resource is the money available for spending in the form of cash, liquid securities and credit lines. Before going into business, an

entrepreneur needs to secure sufficient financial resource in order to be able to operate efficiently and sufficiently well to promote success.

Historical Perspective of Educational Management in Nigeria

Administration and management of education in the 21st century have actively experienced a laudable and historic landmark as Nigerians, took complete control of their destiny in education. Indeed, there are numerous positive landmarks in education in Nigeria presently. In other words, Nigeria has accomplished more in education than during the previous one hundred years of British colonial administrative rule of the country. This period of what we may call home grown (FGN, 2004). Nigerian educational administration and management was greeted with several heights such as issues bordering on national education policies, primary education, secondary education alongside, the Universal Basic Education (UBE) and tertiary education as well as the institutional frameworks for regulating education.

The establishment of over 50 educational institutions within the second quarter of the 21st century is not a common achievement in the history of educational administration, management and development in the country. In spite of this laudable efforts of successive state and federal governments in re-positioning Nigeria education on the world map, Nigerian educational system and its productivity in the 21st Century has continued to suffer some set back; as a result

of misconceived and misdirected social values, corruption and economic instability or economic meltdown (Nwagwu, 2014).

Economic meltdown simply refers to economic depression. It means when the income generated is not up to expenditure. Nigeria has excess capacity for crude oil production but OPEC regulation places a limit on production. The scenario looks grim as the price of the product has suffered a dramatic decline from \$147/barrel in July, 2008 to less than \$40/barrel in January, 2009 (World Bank in Okebukola. 2008). The world was initially optimistic of an early recovery but recent events show that “hopes for swift end of the recession is fading” Also in Nigeria corruption and poor leadership has led to economic stagnation and even decline. This raises the possibility of government control measures, such as cutting down expenditure which may affect statutory allocation to the educational sector. Also it shows that a long period of recession is in place, since Nigeria depends on the Western economies (Akintade, 2013). Definitely this will have an adverse effect on engineering education since statutory allocation to institutions may cease or reduce drastically because of the global economic meltdown.

Educational Management Functions

Educational management is directed at the attainment of educational goals in an effective and efficient manner through planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting and budgeting for education system (Omoike, 2013).

Planning: Planning is a decision making process that concern itself with the line of action to follow in-order to achieve pre-determined organizational goals by the optimal use of available resources.

Organizing: This involves the establishment of a formal structural line of authority and responsibility which defines what is to be done, by whom and how it is to be done. It is the centre point of management because it involves building-up of human and material resources needed for successful attainment of the goals of an organization.

Staffing: Staffing involves the recruitment, selection, appointment, orientation development and remuneration of staff. It is the process of identifying and selecting the most qualified individuals for the vacant position in an organization.

Directing: This is provision of effective leadership through proper decision making. Directing and leading are the interpersonal aspects of management by which subordinates are led to understand and contribute effectively and efficiently to the attainment of enterprise objectives (Kountz and O’Donnel, 1976).

Coordinating: This involves the synchronizing and integration of activities and command and control structure to ensure that the resources of an organization are used most efficiently in pursuit of the specified objectives.

Reporting: This is where communication is very necessary. Reporting ensure feed-back of the job performed from the subordinate to

the super ordinate. It helps the head manager to know the effectiveness of the task carried-out by the subordinates.

Budgeting: Budgeting involves forecasting the future expenditure based on expected revenue. School budgeting as an educational plan with an estimate of the receipt and expenditures is necessary to finance it for a definite period of financing of education.

Financing of Education

Financing of education cuts across all aspects of funding of education, this include sources of fund. Finance is one of the important resources that are needed for the day-to-day running of education; in fact, finance is the live wire of other available resources in education. Its importance cannot be over stressed because no organization can carry-out its functions effectively without adequate financial resources at its disposal. Money is needed to

pay staff, build good structures, provide infrastructures and learning aid, standard classrooms, laboratories for teaching and research, library etc. Education financing therefore, is seen as the process of sourcing, allocating and managing funds of public revenue in the production of educational services for the attainment of desired objectives and it also help to determine the extent of the number of employees and schools system for the efficient and effective production of educational services.

There is no denying fact that education is poorly funded in 21st century in Nigeria which is yet to comply with the UNESCO recommendation that 26% of annual budget be spent on education (UNESCO, 2000). This may be due to economic depression and a host of other factors. The table below shows how education was funded for few years as against UNESCO 26% recommendation.

Table 1: Funding of Education from 1990 -2003 Showing Total Budget Allocation and Percentage Distribution in Nigeria.

Year	Total Budgets	Allocation to Education	Percentage (%)
1990	39.00	1.13	2.90
1991	13.86	1.43	3.70
1992	27.59	2.40	8.70
1993	53.00	8.10	15.28
1994	110.00	10.28	9.33
1995	155.00	10.28	9.33
1996	155.00	10.28	9.33
1997	155.00	12.73	8.21
1998	260.00	26.76	10.27
1999	249.00	27.71	11.12
2000	677.51	50.66	8.36
2001	894.20	62.60	7.10
2002	849.20	62.60	7.10
2003	765.00	13.00	1.81

Source: Odufowokan (2005). Concepts and Issues in Educational Management.

Ikoya (2000) has unequivocally shown in his study, that there is a positive correlation between resources investment on education, efficient and effective management of education resources and national development. Occasionally when we hear of the hundreds of billions budgeted for education in Nigeria, there is the tendency to get carried away, forgetting about the value and exchange rate of Naira. Table 1 clearly shows our very low commitment to education in Nigeria. Budgeting alone is not enough. Funds budgeted must be released as when due, and for the purpose for which it was budgeted. It is very important to budget adequate fund for Primary, Secondary and University education, the resources provided must be prudently managed for the achievement of stated objectives.

In the light of the above therefore, the author examined issues associated with funding of schools, the management of funds in a depressed economy, mainly from the perspective of developing economies such as Nigeria, as well as the issue of adequacy of funds and proper management of education funding in schools.

Education is an instrument for personal, community and national development. But it is also a very big, expensive enterprise. Scholars of cost benefit analysis in education agree that huge benefits accrue from being educated, hence there should be some cost - sharing formula or mechanism among the stakeholders. Scholars in economics and education have often carried out research on the public (government) unit cost of education and the private unit cost of

education. In virtually all cases, the public cost is far higher than the private cost at all levels of education and the second misinterpreted concept is the 26 percent of national budgets recommended for education by UNESCO for developing countries. Nwagwu (2014) affirmed that people argue that the percentage is idealistic and not realistic. This is because a country also need to cater for agriculture for food security, finance health, industries, transportation, housing, defense and security, among other social and economic sectors of national sustainable development. Indeed, without support for these other sectors, the education system cannot grow and develop. Look at what insecurity caused by Boko Haram in the North East of Nigeria has done to education in that zone. Using the UNESCO benchmark as a guide, Nigeria has not done very well in financing education over the decades. For example, between 2000 and 2012, the highest allocation in the national budget range from a high of 13% to 2008 to a low of 6% in 2011 (FGN 2014). As a matter of fact, it has been revealed that the highest percentage of 15.5% of allocation occurred during the military regime in 1978 (Nwagwu, 2014).

Figures from the World Bank (Okebukola 2008) revealed that among 15 developed countries whose ranks Nigeria wants to join by its project Vision 20-2020, Nigeria's percentage of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) allocated to education was only 3%, the lowest, while other countries allocated as average of 6%. We have to do better than the average percentage of annual budget

allocation to education. Billions of naira may simply hide the true situation, as statistics can sometimes be misleading. The Federal Government has created many Parastatals and agencies to generate revenue for education. They include Education Tax Fund paid by companies as 2% of their assessable pre-tax profit. The money generated is shared thus; higher Education 50%. Primary Education 40% and secondary Education 10%. Recently, Tertiary Education Trust Fund was created, and Primary Education Fund was replaced by Universal Basic Education Fund.

Unfortunately some states cannot access their allocation because they are unable or unwilling to provide their 50% counterpart fund. The future of financing of education does not look bright because state and local Governments, parents and institutions are all looking up to Federal Government Allocations and subventions and international bodies like the World Banks, UNDP, UNESCO, UNICEF and others for interventions which are gradually drying up. Most importantly, we must accept that the financing of education is a sharing responsibility.

Finance is a major resource that cannot be compromised in its utilizations in schools (Omoike, 2013). Problems of school management have always been traced to financial consideration. Stakeholders have complained about improper school management in the area of finance. Federal Government decision to deregulate University is mostly connected with management of finance at that tier of

education system. Disruptions in the school calendar are, in most cases traced to the issue of finance. All this relates to inadequate supply of funds or inadequate utilization or management of funds made available for education. The primary channel of proper fund management in school system is through the budget. The budget is a plan which provide estimate of future revenue and expenditure. It is a tool to guide school administrators in the judicious management of available fund. As a plan, the school budget is influenced by variety of factors that usually result in modification of the budget. There are two major categories of budget-capital budget and recurrent budget.

From available data, funding education in Nigeria since the inception of the 21st Century till date has not met the 26% of the total budget in any year, and most avenues of funding education has been struck down by economy depression. The various sources that are capable of funding education are enumerated below:

Sources of Financing Education in Nigeria

1. Budgetary Allocation
2. Tuition Fees
3. Industrial Organization
4. Philanthropists
5. Communities
6. Old students Association/Alumni Associations
7. Parents Teachers Association (P.T.A)
8. Religious Organizations
9. School Revenue Yielding Ventures
10. Education Tax Fund (E. T. F)

11. Sale of School Farm Produce, e.t.c.

Adeyemi (2011) further suggested other sources of financing education in Nigeria. Such suggestions include the raising bank loans for capital development, introduction of property tax, donations from endowment, donations from parents/teachers associations, education tax, development levy, taxes from lotteries to finance education and donations from alumni associations. According to Odufowokan (2007), other sources available to education financing in Nigeria are basically three, these are the public authorities, the user of education and self-generated income.

Public Authorities: Public educational institutions are financed majorly by the owner - government, which raised her resources through taxation, foreign loans and grants. The first means which is taxation is normally raised for the general purposes of government such as provision of education, good roads, health services, good drinkable water among others. The government allocates a sizeable proportion of its annual budget, in form of subventions, to the provision and financing of education. Famade (2014) asserts that in support of the above, said the government put in place the Education Tax Fund in 1994 which mandated companies operating in Nigeria to pay 2 percent of their annual profit as Education Tax.

Foreign Loans and Grants: These also provide another source of finance for education. These are sometimes called bilateral and multi-lateral loans and grants . According to Famade (2000) about N120

million World Bank loan was secured in 1992 by the Federal government for Primary Education Project. This same type of loan has been sourced for the Universities, Polytechnics, and Colleges of Education. On foreign aids, the most recent trend now is the unrestricted offer of scholarships for specialized training outside the country.

User of Education: The trade-off between the income and the expenditure on education has necessitated the introduction of school fees in the face of falling public revenue due to economic melt-down and the depressed economy. Odufowokan (2007) asserts that the constant fall in the price of crude oil and allied products in the world market supported the idea of tuition fee, development fee, workshop fee and so on. In addition to cost of textbook, registration and examination fee alongside P.T.A. levy, caution fee-in respect of anticipated damages that are never reimbursed, most recently, the introduction of Parents Forum fund in tertiary institutions where these unending problems and financing problems are discussed.

Internally Generated Income (IGR): This is another major source of educational financing that is done through the establishment of revenue generating projects like bookshops, farms, petrol stations, pure water, soap and packaging, fee-charged for parking spaces and consultancy. The newest dimension to this is the establishment of hostel and catering services named Institutions Guest Houses. It was made clear in the policy that "In pursuance of these objectives, "Primary education shall be

compulsory, free, universal and qualitative”. Therefore, from the cardinal objectives above, primary education input is expected to produce two category of Nigerians. The first are those who would prepare physically, mentally, socially, morally and spiritually to functionally serve and contribute to the development of the socio-political and economic growth of the nation. The other category are those who would be admitted to study, in the post primary institution within and outside the country (FGN, 2014). It is therefore important to state clearly that, any mistake made in producing substandard quality manpower at this foundation level, will produce a recurring problem in all facets of the society. This was strongly accepted in Akinyemi, (1982) Identification of some basic problems of primary education which includes:

- i. Expansion of primary education without due regard to adequate teacher strength.
- ii. General lack of systemic planning of primary education activities.
- iii. Haphazard school inspection by ministry inspectors.
- iv. Inadequate and insufficient instructional material-textbooks, modern teaching aids.
- v. Inadequate financing and poorly managed resources.
- vi. Ineffective management of schools
- vii. Obsolete supervisory techniques by teacher educators.

viii. Over enrolment resulting in overcrowded classroom.

ix. Poor physical facilities- school buildings and classrooms.

These observations above were made over two decades ago but the situation on ground is more sympathetic. A close look at the observed items above shows that almost all the listed items above rest squarely on inadequate funding especially item i, iv v, vii, viii and ix because with adequate funding and prudent management, adequate teachers strength would be enhanced and overcrowded classroom averted. Also the problem of inadequate and insufficient instructional materials would not have existed. Similarly, the issue of physical facilities would have been settled. Aghenta (1989) corroborate this view, maintaining that the success of any school rests on the resources made available to it. He argued that all other vital element in the school can be obtained if adequate fund is made available.

Managing Education and National Development

Education is beloved to be the greatest instrument which can be used to bring about changes. This is the greatest investment a nation can make for the development of its economic, sociological and human resources. The federal government in its national policy on education has emphasized the role of education as an instrument for ensuring national development (FGN, 2014). Hence, managing education has become the main agenda for using education as a tool

for societal and overall development which will be sustainable.

Implications of a Depressed Economy on Education

In the past few years there have been myriads of administrative problems confronting the educational system in Nigeria. The system has not only witnessed decayed facilities and infrastructures, poor funding, poor quality products, low morale of teachers, incessant crisis and inadequate research, but also that the government of Nigeria has been saddled with too many responsibilities; it does not seem to be able or willing to provide solution for solving these problems. These problems have become a recurring demand in the history of Nigerian education. For many years, budgets of education have been under enormous pressure as a result of declining budgetary allocation and increase in enrolment and shortfalls from Nigerian Universities Commission funds. The effect of this on education management is better imagined. In spite of the efforts of different donor countries in providing assistance for education; the system still lacks the necessary fund and materials to implement the various programmes (Udey, Ebuara, Ekpoh and Edet, 2009).

The situation has become worst due to current global financial crisis which has impacted on the world economy and the fall in oil price in the world market. Dependence on crude oil for the survival of the economy is needless at this particular period of time; exploiting other avenues for the survival of

the economy is most paramount. But economy depression has in one way or the other obstructed the above listed sources of funds to education. Economic depression is more felt in a developing and third world countries whose economy even in the best of time have been very vulnerable. The economy is characterized by the following:

1. An economy that does not support the minimum wages ensuring level required for basic living
2. An economy with high rate/level of unemployment.
3. An economy with low industrial utilization
4. An economy with low level of social security.
5. An economy with a high child mortality rate.
6. An economy with low life expectancy
7. An economy with poor social infrastructure
8. Finally, it is an economy with little or no funds for education.

Managing education in a depressed economy will therefore be a very difficult task if depressed economy is characterized by the above listed characteristics/features. Education on this ground experience a geometric setback and some of the challenges that will be faced are discussed below;

1. Unstable staff: This will occur due to poor earning of teachers many people will now be using teaching as a stepping stone to a more attractive job. This could make teaching

profession for fresh graduates just doing it until they find better jobs.

2. Inadequate classrooms: Classroom that is over-crowded with up to ninety (90) students in a classroom designed for about thirty (30) students will come to play in a depressed economy. As such chairs may not be enough and some students and up pairing thereby have room for distractions such as piercing each other's ear.
3. Inadequate learning equipment: Another problem faced when managing education in a depressed economy is inadequate leaning equipments for science practical classes, this will no doubt affect the learning process. All of these prevail and the host of others.

The above has a lot of implications on Nation's Development in no small measure. The goals of a nation like Nigeria such as:-

- a. Standard minimum wages
- b. High rate of employment
- c. Economy stability
- d. Political stability
- e. Social stability
- f. High rate of security
- g. High rate of infrastructure

But all the problems of managing education in a depressed economy listed in this paper among others can hamper national development. Therefore, managing education in a depressed economy has put an obstacle to the development of ensuring standard minimum wages, high rate of

employment, political stability, economy stability, high rate of security and the five national goals spelt out by National Policy on Education (NPE). This is because "once the education of a nation is hampered, no meaningful development can take place."

Conclusion

Education satisfies basic human need for knowledge, provides a means of helping to meet other basic needs, and helps sustain and accelerate overall development. The management of the education sector in Nigeria is faced with a depressed economy which affects proper funding of its sectors including education. The fund made available to education sector is being affected as a result of the economic meltdown experienced worldwide and the recent fall of naira against Dollar. This paper therefore, concludes that proper management of the education is required in order to maintain and improve the standard in the education sector which could lead to societal growth and national development.

Suggestions

From the foregoing, it is suggested that;

1. There should be new orientation in order to have strong consciousness and commitment toward our nations' educational development, management and administration.
2. The entire management and administration of the nation's education should be in hands of the professionals and expertise in the field. In order words, political favoritism should be avoided, if

standard and quality is to be put in place; especially during recession.

3. There should be prudent management of resources by school administrators for realization of education goals.
4. Government should ensure that money meant for the education sector is released for its purpose.

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